

COMPACTION BEHAVIOR OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATE DURING CURE

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ABSTRACT

Compaction behavior of Graphite/Epoxy laminates during the autoclave curing process was investigated by measuring the change of the laminate thickness. A device which can monitor the change of the laminate thickness was developed using a strain gage attached sensor. The sensor was found to be unaffected by the temperature variation from 20°C up to 150°C. Sixteen plies of Graphite/Epoxy prepregs were layed up and cured in an autoclave at four different temperatures, namely, 90, 100, 110 and 120°C under the cure pressure of 30 psig to observe the effect of the cure temperature on the compaction of the laminate. The effect of the cure pressure was observed by curing the laminate under 0, 30 and 60 psig (101, 308 and 515 kPa, respectively) at 120°C. From the experiments, it was found that the total compaction of the laminate was same regardless of the variation in the cure temperature and pressure. The rate of compaction, however, showed variation for the different cure temperatures and pressures. Experiments showed that the continuous thickness monitoring method developed aids in determining the cure cycle as well as verifying the proposed cure models.

INTRODUCTION

The determination of the cure cycle of composite has imposed many problems to both prepreg manufactures and the end users of the prepregs. In order to optimize the cure cycle, compaction behavior of the prepreg as well as the resin cure kinetics must be studied. With the differential scanning calorimeter and other thermal analyzing systems which give data in a continuous form, the cure kinetics measurement is relatively simple. On the contrary, there is no continuous monitoring method available for the observation of the compaction behavior of the composite. Hence, the experimenter must run many batches of autoclave curing in order to gather the sufficient number of data points.

Models describing the compaction and the resin flow were proposed by Loos and Springer [1] and Gutowsky [2] to alleviate the problem mentioned above. However, the models require that some constants be determined by measuring either the resin flow or the compaction as a function of time. The procedures described by the above authors [1, 2] are very time consuming and cumbersome since data cannot be taken continuously.

The objective of this investigation therefore is to provide an efficient way to measure the compaction of the laminate as a function of time to help the understanding of the resin flow mechanism and simplify the determination of the proper cure cycle.

EXPERIMENTS

Measuring System and the Sensor

A schematic of the measuring system is shown in Fig.1. The thickness measuring sensor was placed between two composite laminates of the same dimension (70 mm x 50 mm, 16 plies thick). Each laminate was surrounded by a steel dam to prevent the resin flow in the plane of the prepreg ply. The steel dams were supported at the bottom with a very weak spring and allowed to move up and down in the grooves on the tool plate. A perforated steel plate was placed on the top of the two laminates. On the top of the perforated steel plate bleeders were placed. The whole layup assembly was vacuum bagged and 29 in Hg (3.1 kPa) of vacuum was pulled.

As composite plies are compacted, the perforated steel plate moves down causing the three point bending bar deflected downward by pressing the contact block (Fig.1). The amount of the deflection of the bar is detected by strain gages attached to the bending bar. The gage signal is then amplified by a strain amplifier. The whole layup as shown in Fig.1 was put in an autoclave and the signal was recorded on a strip chart recorder.

Temperature induced error of the sensor was checked by varying the

All Units in mm.

Fig. 1. Schematics of the sensor and the measuring system:
 a) the sensor; b) the bending bar; and c) the measuring system.

temperature from 20°C to 150°C. The maximum induced error was within +1% of the whole measuring range of 0.7 mm.

The relationship between the displacement and the gage signal of the sensor was determined using a calibrator for extensometers (Model 4MBR of Boeckler Instruments). The calibration factor was found to be 4490 $\mu\text{E}/\text{mm}$ and the linearity error was about 0.2% within the measuring range.

Compaction Tests

To observe the effect of the cure temperature during the cure process the compaction as a function of time of Graphite/Epoxy laminates were measured for four different cure temperatures of 90, 100, 110 and 120°C under 30 psig (308 kPa). Experiments were also performed to find the effect of cure pressure for three different cure pressures of 0, 30 and 60 psig (101, 308 and 515 kPa, respectively) at 90°C. Sixteen plies of Graphite/Epoxy prepregs (Model CEP100NS unidirectional tape by Lucky Co., Korea) cut to a size of 50mm X 70mm were layed up and cured at each condition. The heat-up rate used was 2°C/min. The signal recorded on the strip chart recorder was converted to actual decrease in the laminate thickness using the calibration factor explained in the previous section. Since there were some scatters in the "uncompacted" laminate thicknesses, data were presented in relative compaction. The relative compaction is related to the measured compaction by

$$\text{Relative compaction} = \frac{\text{Measured Compaction}}{\text{Uncompacted Laminate Thickness}} \quad (1)$$

As shown in Fig.2-a, the relative compactions as a function of time for each temperature collapse in a single curve for the first 30 minutes (till the temperature reaches 90°C) due to the same heat-up rate. The rate of compaction then starts to vary for each cure temperature. While the times required to reach the "complete compaction" are different, the total compactions are independent of the cure temperature. This implies that for the current test condition resin gels after the compaction is completed. This situation will become different for thicker laminates where the "complete compaction" cannot be reached.

Fig. 2. Compaction as a function of time a) for different cure temperatures and b) for different cure pressures. Heat-up rate used was $2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ for all the tests. Throughout the cure cycle 29 in Hg of vacuum was applied. The layup sequence for all the laminates was $[\text{O}_{16}]_{\text{T}}$.

Fig.2-b shows the relative compaction as a function of time for each cure pressure. As can be seen the rate of compaction and the time to reach the "complete compaction" strongly depend upon the cure pressure. From Fig.2-b the times required to reach the "complete compaction" are 50, 70 and 90 minutes for 0, 30 and 60 psig, respectively. Total compaction, however, remains almost constant regardless of the cure pressure (22% for 0 psig and 23.5 % for 30 and 60 psig) since the compaction is thought to be completed even at the lowest cure pressure. This again will not be the case for thicker laminates where larger cure pressure is required to ensure the complete compaction.

As can be seen in Fig.2-a and Fig.2-b, time needed to complete the compaction of the laminate can easily be determined for different cure pressures and temperatures. Along with resin cure kinetics data which give the time required for complete cure of the resin, the method described presents an effective tool for determination of the composite cure cycle.

CONCLUSIONS

The measuring system used in this paper for monitoring the thickness change of composite laminate during cure was found out to be reliable and gave satisfactory results for a wide range of different cure conditions. It was shown that the measuring system can be used to determine the optimal cure cycle as well as to verify the resin flow models. Furthermore the compaction signal can be fed back to the autoclave control system to accomplish a better control of autoclave cure process variables.

REFERENCES

1. Loos, A.C. and Springer, G. S., "Curing of Epoxy Matrix Composites," Journal of Composite Materials, 1983, 17, 135-169.
2. Gutowsky, T. G., "A Resin Flow Model/Fiber Deformation Model for Composites," SAMPE Quarterly, 1985, 16, 58-64.